

How Head Teachers Motivate: Exploring Perceptions of Teachers about Head-Teachers Motivational Techniques at Higher Education

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Abstract

Motivation is a key aspect of every workplace if the workforce is to function effectively and efficiently. This study explores that leadership in higher institutions of education in KPK Pakistan, looking at a typical set of 12 male and 12 female higher institutes. The aim was to offer a picture of the current situation, as perceived by principals and teachers, and to explore differences in their perceptions. The views of the Heads of the Institutions (Principals) and a sample of their teachers were gathered using a questionnaire. This suggests that there may well be two very different kinds of motivations atmospheres in the sample of colleges surveyed. Secondly, where teachers tend to respond well to a supportive, affirmative approach on the leadership, where they feel valued and good work is praised, as well as being given the freedom and trust to innovate, the Principals tend to a more authoritarian approach.

Key Words:

Motivation,
Performance,
Higher
Education,
Heads,
Teachers,
Motivational
Techniques.

Introduction

The need for motivation is often presented as some kind of explanation for behavior in learning. Thus, teachers sometimes despair about the lack of motivation in their students while principals may reflect that some teachers need motivation. Thus, it may be argued that encouraging motivation is a key tool that would be used by higher education institutional heads currently in working place. Heads might use motivation techniques within the work atmosphere to encourage teachers to figure, each severally and on social occasions, to create the most

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effective results for getting ready most beneficially and competently. It had been recognized that motivation should be sent everything considered, at any rate, it is before long valuing that every individual has his one of kind ways of action of drive powers. It is the dedication of the heads of foundations to effectively see and address these, inducing powers (Daft, 2007). The motivation of academics has been an important concern of the faculty and college directors. Every teacher ought to worry regarding motivation (Moorhead, 2007).

Many factors determine how people are motivated.

Figure 1. Factors of Teacher Motivation

Motivation, within the broadest plan of the term, maybe a task to clarify why the direct happens (e.g., why individuals do what they do). The majority of teachers believe that motivation is a pre-basic for learning. Behaviorists, in any case, consider it to be a protection, a consequence of learning since it is, itself, learned. Motivation is moving others to achieve something since they have to do it (Cook, 2008). Motivation starts from inside so it is dependent upon each individual to drive him/herself (Greenberg, 2006).

Motivation indicates an expression that sorts out the lead of the person to express targets. Motivation has been depicted as the psychological outlined as the mental philosophy that gives an irritable explanation and the manner (Kreitner, 1995). Teachers motivate students through several methods of reasoning dependent on comprehension of a student's improvement and progress structures, sole breaking point contrasts, and of inner and outside parts that may stimulate and keep up the desire to take in extra. Heads of associations have comparable commitments and openings with the teaching staff. (Espinosa, 2006).

Heads need to give the advantage of dynamic atmosphere to guarantee that their teachers can see that, by advancing toward the authentic and institutional objectives. They are, moreover, accomplishing their unusual section goals. These goals could be such things as money related prizes or individual prizes, for example, the regard of their accomplices or work fulfillment or a mix of any

number of things that the teacher considers being essential. It is no extraordinary giving someone a remunerating rise on the off chance that they are disappointed with the movement and they do not believe cash to be a significant factor in their working life (Peters, 1992).

Teachers' motivation regularly needs to do with the attitude of teachers in association with work. It needs to do with their desire to look into the educational strategies inside the college condition. It needs to do with their energy for students' requests and management, significantly within the classroom. Therefore, it may motivate their affiliation or exclusion in educational and non-educational activities, that add a school. The teacher is the one that separates the academic rationale and objectives into an information teacher is the one that separates the educational rationale and objectives into data, understandings, and frames of mind that enable the students to create and make in their thinking, appreciation, and capacities. The classroom climate is fundamental to teacher motivation. On the likelihood that a teacher experiences the classroom as an ensured, sound, the happy spot with constant resources and workplaces for teaching, for good learning, he/she can, in general, take a premium quite anticipated throughout the time spent organization, association and also the general upgrade of the school and college. The teacher directs and transmits the image of one who upgrades learning and so the physical conditions of the classroom through deliberateness, request, and management. He makes an investigation of students' assessments and views derived by their lead and response inside the classroom condition (Griffin, 2008).

A domain that continues educational motivation is often created within the home, assessment within the classroom, or during a whole school or college. One amongst the foremost effective ways that of causing inspiration and creating motivational forces among student in the college culture. The college and school culture can be thick and changed through channels, for instance, shared characteristics, hallowed people, traditions, cutoff points, stories, and social structures (Deal, 1987). Leadership might be characterized as the power that specific people (pioneers) apply upon the objective accomplishment of others (subordinates) in a hierarchical setting. Authority and motivational characteristics are surprising to have among foundation in training, as well as among teachers also. The heads must know to prime associations in which administration and basic leadership are united, and constant studying is encouraged for parents, students as well as teachers (Bernard, 1995).

Every teacher is similarly imperative to the achievement of an organization. Leadership needs that individual touch by trying to know every teacher by name and seeing a portion of the teacher's expectations, fears, and desires. Mifflin (1995) sees that every teacher has something to contribute and needs the regard of those above. One of the most important vital attributes of a pioneer in uprightness. The head ought to be agreeable and steady in all associations with staff individuals and make a positive workplace. He will prepare and advance the teachers (Beerrens,

2000). The essence of demonstrable skill requires a make a beeline for serving the interests of the teacher and their staff and to hold fast to the ideas of authority, greatness, trustworthiness, respectability, and regard for other people (Gibson et al., 2004).

The teacher's task is to keep eye on the job characteristics. These describe what has to be done, with some indication of purpose and method. Hopefully, such a set of characteristics outlines the variety of tasks involved, with a description of the kind of person who will be able to undertake the tasks. This may generate interest and motivation in its own right (Bayrs & Rue, 1996:). Job security is one of the best objectives that arouse representatives. Heads need to impart and clear up hierarchical strategy and talk about professional stability to their teachers (Luthans, 1995). The selection of remunerations, acknowledgment, censures, or disciplines to spur staff extends the style of leadership (Knezevich, 2005). The head's position of authority (responder and director) add to the confidence of teachers, either by encouraging an unpleasant environment or by supporting and working together with them (Owens, 2006)

Motivation is an inner state, within the individual. External factors may affect this and these may include external various goals attractive like incentives and rewards in the sense of extrinsic and intrinsic rewards and cash or recognition. Nonetheless, such external circumstances must translate into internal perspectives. Motivating leadership is a key but defining exactly the nature of such leadership is never easy. Much depends on personal characteristics and the practical inter-relationships that arise from these. Overall, motivating leadership together with high morale among teachers will create a favorable image for the institution (Cenzo & Robbins, 1998).

Money is a tangible reinforcer since its belongings and human can be beneficiary through various practices (Lewis, 1998). Another motivational technique that is acknowledgment, is one of the most powerful motivators for enhanced execution. Acknowledgment could incorporate open acclaim, the extension of an occupation examination, or exceptional consideration. Its adequacy to inspiration relies on the individual (teacher) concerning what esteem and position he provides for the acknowledgment of the head (Ricks et al., 1995). Nevertheless, a lot of this examination is drawn from the universe of business and industry and may not make an interpretation of effectively into an instructive organization where the last 'items' are not effortlessly evaluated: it is difficult to quantify the 'creation' of a knowledgeable student.

Encouragement statements like 'extraordinary,' 'great,' 'superb' and 'fine', related to acceptable performance is powerful motivational forces. The Encouragement offered a response from the top to assist teachers and students to stay up to their undertakings in college assignments. Support gives data about execution and builds self – worth, yet successful consolation must be founded on teachers' genuine presentation (Reeve, 2001). Nonetheless, the teacher frequently

needs that amazing motivation got by seeing understudies improving, accomplishing something unrealistic previously, and, maybe, students getting to be mindful that they have gained ground in their investigations.

Ofoeqbu (2004) discusses that needs of the teacher not just change and an ordinary bit of remuneration and settlement, yet in like manner the correct improvement and working environments for achievable investigation lobby update the association and educational setup. Hukamdad (2004) thought that a significant number of teachers did not have any important bearing the suitable structures of direct adjustment, yet rather they were insensible of these forefront systems and study hall the executives.

Perhaps the teachers are to feel valued and resources of the tasks that are a great inspiration for motivational teachers in hand. Figure 1 illustrates some of the factors which are important here.

Figure 2. Sources of Teacher Motivation

Objectives of the Study

The key focus objective of this research work was to explore the construct of teachers concerning the motivational techniques employed by the heads of institutions of higher education (known as Principals) to encourage academics to form most efforts for an excellent performance. To assist them to attain this main objective, the subsequent specific objectives were identified:

1. To study the perceptions of teachers about the effective and ineffective motivational techniques used by their heads.
2. To find out the impact of motivational techniques used by the heads on the performance of teachers.

Methods and Materials

Research Design

The strength of this piece of research work is to discover how teachers and principals see their motivational techniques in connection with the execution of teachers. The investigation plans to be unique, to distinguish the impression of the two groups and a sticking point where these recognitions do not correspond. An assessment was utilized to pick up the perspectives of the two teachers and principals.

Population

The population of the study comprised the gathering of respondents of the considerable number of heads of higher institutions in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province in Pakistan and all the teacher's instructors working in higher institutions.

Sampling

A random sample of principals of 12 male and 12 female higher institutions, with five teachers from each higher Institution, was selected. This gives 24 principals and 120 teachers in all the selected sample.

Tools of Research

This investigation included a gathering of strong information from essential sources accessible in the higher institutes in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Surveys were utilized as research instruments for the gathering of information. Two surveys were produced, each utilizing Likert (1932) type explanations, with answers being given a Likert scale based on a five-point scale from 'strongly agree' and up to 'strongly disagree'. One questionnaire was for principals and another questionnaire for teachers.

The fundamental highlights of the surveys identified with the motivational techniques that were included by the principals of higher institutions. These related to important and optimistic expressions of the principals, appreciation for bona fide undertakings, positive lead, lacking creativity, progression, statement of want for the principals, heading, gratefulness to develop a clever tendency, award with

overwhelming titles, verbal or nonverbal affirmation, extraordinary relationship with principal, contribution on academic execution, typical appraisal of teachers and money like cash related budgetary motivating force and finance incentives.

Data Analysis

For validity purposes, each question was checked and each item of questions of responses developed was considered. In the like manner, addresses that had been utilized by both teachers and principals, it was possible to consider their responses using chi-square (χ^2) like a conceivable test. For data analysis purposes, chi-square using was used as a statistical technique so, no occasion is taken into account as an impact gathering. The request being attended is whether or not the social affairs fluctuated in their responses from one another. They are thought of two by two: do the Principals and teachers react in varied manners?

The results for every request are showing up as rates for simplicity, and the application of chi-square estimations are completed and also using the repeat data. The data gathering is done very precisely where any class falls under 5% or 5 respondents, whichever is progressively essential, and the degrees of chance is decreased suitably. The models are according to the accompanying principals: N = 24 Teachers: N = 120.

Firstly, the overall responses, the general reactions of the principals are considered. For convenience, the following tables demonstrate the results for the 10 inquiries.

Results and Discussion

Overall Responses

20 questions used by the principals are considered first, followed by 20 questions used with teachers. All data are presented as percentages for clarity.

Table 1. Principals' Responses –1

Principals (N = 24)						
The Principal		%				
		SA	A	UD	D	SD
1	Constructive and optimistic	40	20	5	25	10
2	Innovative	38	28	11	10	13
3	Appreciates his teachers' work openly	2	10	6	44	38
4	stiff in his dealings	20	32	3	28	17
5	Personal loyalty to the teachers	10	19	5	36	30
6	Expectations better performance	30	45	2	13	10

7	Develop a sense of humor	45	25	5	15	10
8	Recognition with notable titles	30	48	6	6	10
9	Scolds the teachers on their mistakes	19	47	5	15	14
10	Punctual	30	35	6	15	14

The principals here are describing themselves. Unquestionably, they may be impossible now and again, seeing themselves in a to a great degree positive way or, no doubt, they may be over-wary of themselves. An extraordinary piece of the data shows noteworthy polarization of viewpoints, with some being greatly positive and some uncommonly negative. They may reflect some being over-optimistic with others being over-fundamental. The response to address 3 recommends that the Principals are not being straightforwardly esteemed, but instead, tend to be over-essential being alluded to 9.

Table 2. Principals’ Responses – 2

Principals (N = 24)		%				
The Principal		SA	A	UD	D	SD
11	Acknowledgments and Achievements	25	43	2	15	15
12	Teachers' egos	43	26	5	20	6
13	sympathetic behaviors	35	47	4	5	9
14	Encouragement	30	38	7	17	8
15	Appropriate workload.	39	28	3	25	5
16	Professional competition	8	24	5	43	20
17	Role model	28	44	7	15	6
18	Fair play	23	39	12	8	18
19	Disciplinary matters	10	8	5	47	30
20	Annual confidential reports	41	25	4	24	6

While many patterns of responses show the same strong polarization, the principals tend to see themselves as sympathetic, supportive, and caring. They see themselves as concerned about the teacher's ego, encouraging, fair in academic and disciplinary matters, and, in general, trying to do a good job.

Table 3. Teacher Responses – 1

Teachers (N = 120)		%				
Principal Enhance the Performance Teachers Due To		SA	A	UD	D	SD
1	The constructive and optimistic attitude of the Principal	26	53	6	11	4

2	Reinforcement for creativity and innovation	30	49	5	9	7
3	Commitments on genuine efforts	18	50	6	16	10
4	Stiff dealing	9	10	3	24	54
5	Personal trust and loyalty	46	37	4	7	6
6	Expressions of expectations	31	48	3	12	6
7	Sense of humor develop foe gratitude	22	51	4	13	10
8	Recognition with notable titles	46	28	2	14	10
9	Scolding on mistake	43	30	3	16	8
10	The regularity of the Principal	45	39	2	8	6

In looking at the responses of the teachers, it is clear that the teachers value constructive and affirmative leadership and see the scope for creativity and freedom to innovate is important. They reject the more authoritarian approaches and seem to see over-correction as counterproductive.

Table 4. Teacher Responses - 2

Teachers (N =120)						
Principal Enhance the Performance Teachers Due To		%				
		SA	A	UD	D	SD
11	Acknowledgment and achievement	35	41	4	11	9
12	Cares of self-respect	28	43	4	14	11
13	Showing Sympathetic behavior	51	26	3	11	9
14	Encouragement on hardworking	32	43	6	9	10
15	Assignment of appropriate workload	37	43	5	9	6
16	Professional competition	48	28	4	12	8
17	Good actions as a role model	28	52	3	7	10
18	Fair play in all academic matters	21	47	4	19	9
19	Strictness in disciplinary matters	43	31	4	18	4
20	Unrealistically writing annual confidential reports	5	11	2	36	46

The responses paint an overall picture where teachers were to be respected and encouraged, where they are treated sympathetically and equitably. They accept the need for discipline and high standards and seem to like the idea of competition.

Looking at the responses of the principals and the teachers leaves an impression of considerable divergence of view. To see if this divergence is significant in statistical terms, the response patterns are now compared.

Comparative Responses: Principals and Teachers

Table 5. Constructive and Optimistic Attitude of the Principal Enhances the Performance of the Teachers.

	SA	A	N	D	SD	Comparisons	χ^2	df	p
Principals	42	21	4	25	8	Principals/Teachers	10.0	3	< 0.001
Teachers	25	53	6	11	4				

The differences in perceptions suggest that teachers are less polarised in their views and, overall, the principles do not appreciate their role in enhancing performance clearly as do the teachers.

Table 6: Appreciations on Genuine Efforts Motivates a Teacher to do Even Better.

	SA	A	N	D	SD	Comparisons	χ^2	df	p
Principals	4	8	4	46	38	Principals/Teachers	28.3	2	< 0.001
Teachers	18	49	6	17	10				

There is quite a dramatic difference in perspectives here. Expressing appreciation is a powerful motivating effect as the teachers are aware. It is a matter of concern that the principal takes an almost opposite viewpoint.

Table 7. Stiff Handling Principal Enhances the Performance of the Teacher.

	SA	A	N	D	SD	Comparisons	χ^2	df	p
Principals	21	33	4	25	17	Principals/Teachers	13.9	3	< 0.001
Teachers	9	10	7	24	53				

This explains the differences seen in table 6. While the teachers grasp that appreciation is a powerful motivator, the principles think in terms of discipline. While setting standards is important, motivation is rarely enhanced by a lack of appreciation on the part of managers.

Table 8. The Personal loyalty of the Principal Enhances the Performance of the Teacher.

	SA	A	N	D	SD	Comparisons	χ^2	df	p
Principals	8	21	4	38	29	Principals/Teachers	33.5	3	< 0.001

Teachers	46	38	3	8	6				
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This is related to the previous table. Again, the principles fail to appreciate that it is important that teachers feel personally supported. This is the key for motivation.

Table 9. Indiscriminately Enjoyment of Fringe Benefits Causes Better Performance

	SA	A	N	D	SD	Comparisons	χ^2	df	p
Principals	8	25	4	21	42	Principals/ Teachers	24.1	2	< 0.001
Teachers	48	29	2	14	8				

Principals and teachers hold almost opposite views.

Table 10. Apprehension for Transfer Affects the Performance of the Teacher.

	SA	A	N	D	SD	Comparisons	χ^2	df	p
Principals	17	21	13	21	29	Principals/ Teachers	10.7	2	< 0.01
Teachers	32	40	2	12	15				

The principals hold a diversity of views while the majority of teachers are apprehensive about transfer possibilities. The significant minority of apprehensive teachers are perhaps those who are well-established and transfer holds no fears or those who are very young and unencumbered with family responsibilities.

Table 11. Forcefully Expression of Opinions affects the Performance of the Teacher.

	SA	A	N	D	SD	Comparisons	χ^2	df	p
Principals	17	13	8	38	25	Principals/ Teachers	12.1	2	< 0.01
Teachers	34	32	4	14	16				

This set of data is consistent with the patterns shown in tables 7 and 8. Teachers want to be supported and affirmed. This enhances motivation. They do not want to be pressurized or harassed. Of course, there will be occasions where principals will have to state things bluntly. However, people are always functioning at their best when they feel valued, not when they feel bullied.

Table 12. The Principal allows duties to his teachers according to their choice and interest.

	SA	A	N	D	SD	Comparisons	χ^2	df	p
Principals	8	25	8	25	33	Principals/ Teachers	10.5	2	< 0.01
Teachers	45	23	2	13	17				

Again, the two groups show very different views, although the limitations of chi-square do not show this fully. Teachers think their choice and interests are being met, all the principals claim that they do not aim for that.

Table 13. The Principal gives verbal or nonverbal recognition to the teachers.

	SA	A	N	D	SD	Comparisons	χ^2	df	p
Principals	30	39	5	19	7	Principals/ Teachers	11.4	3	< 0.01
Teachers	51	34	2	10	3				

Both groups have positive views. However, the principals are less confident. This is an interesting example of one group thinking they are doing something much more than the group receiving the action.

Table 14. The Principal Provides Job Security to his Teachers

	SA	A	N	D	SD	Comparisons	χ^2	df	p
Principals	16	20	7	27	30	Principals/ Teachers	18.4	4	< 0.001
Teachers	36	31	5	18	10				

There is a wide divergence of views. This likely indicates that Principals do not see the role as that of offering job security while teachers are looking for such security and see it vested in the Principals.

Discussion

Looking at the comparisons overall, there are consistent and wide differences between the perceptions of teachers and their Principals. Perhaps the most important difference is the deduction that teachers tend to see the motivation in terms of affirmation while Principals tend to see the motivation in terms of

direction and discipline. This identifies a clear need to work in the training of Principals.

One other interesting feature is that, in almost every question, for both groups, there is a strong measure of polarisation of views. In other words, some tend to agree or to disagree, often strongly. There are few who hold intermediate positions. This suggests that we have two populations in the sample and it may reflect the different experiences of teachers in different colleges, some being much more strongly affirmed by the principals who have grasped something of the way to motivate while others feel pressurized and unvalued, perhaps reflecting the way their principals are treating them.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study offers a picture of the way principals in the higher institutions are operating in the context of motivating their staff as well as the way the teachers see the motivational approaches of the principals. Of course, the views of the two groups do not always coincide. Of course, in surveys like this, there is no certainty that the picture being presented is accurate. This is not because of any intrinsic unreliability or even dishonesty. The problem is that principals and teachers may not see things exactly as they are. Indeed, they may simply tend to see things at times the way they *would like them to be*. Nonetheless, the pictures obtained will be useful as they show how the two groups see things.

The aim is that principals will develop the skills so that their teachers are motivated. Motivated teachers are bound to play out their obligations well. In this manner, educational institutions may accomplish a great standard.

The teachers would, in general, consider sure to be in their principals as motivational: the beneficial and optimistic perspective of the principals, vitality about true attempts, and positive direction. The teachers esteemed the help of imaginativeness, progression, expressions of want by the principals, course, a hilarious tendency, verbal or nonverbal affirmation, extraordinary relationship with principal, analysis on academic execution, standard evaluation of teachers, and fiscal propelling powers. These all give off an impression of being immovably motivational and energize extraordinary execution.

Normal installment of pay and other compensation, the arrangement of instructional innovation, a suitable alleviation time, a strong situation, professional stability, opportunity of activity, and trust in instructors are additional parts of creating motivation.

Principals state that they believe and confidence in their teachers, share the responsibility and master to their teachers, and grant a chance of promotion to their teachers. Most teachers do not provide shortcoming to their heads while they are capable to compete among teachers, the course of action of teacher professional

development, and ready to operate like expert strength as a motivation factor; they are every so often stressed over the possible trade.

A few parts of the conduct of principals have negative effects on teachers. These incorporate apparent bias through inappropriate utilization of leave rules, the discrepancy in a task of examination responsibilities, separation in incidental advantages, nonappearance of employer stability, the absence of input on academic issues, and irregular assessment of the teacher.

Teachers' motivation and self-belief enhance if they will be highly motivated and if their feelings, thinking, and actions are more useful to what are they doing (see figure 2). The principal has a massive degree to assurance their teachers to self-respect, ego, self-esteem, and their dignity that something will happen or that something will work as described as their teachers' response is so more motivated. They may have chances to make sure that resourcing is pleasant. They can't assurance that culture, tradition, and society respects teachers. They can't promise that something will happen or that something will work as described that a community of people and all the good people of the society respect the teachers and give him value. Teachers cannot secure acceptable support from a college, yet they can assurance that what financing is accessible utilized sharply and honestly.

Nonetheless, where principals have remarkable and interesting open doors in the structure up an attitude in the college with the aim that the teachers, just and got together look that what are they doing and act. By offering assistance, sensible checking with comfort, and indicating individual reliability, much will be practiced, teachers should be esteemed. They need the trust and opportunity which state undeniably that they are seen as capable specialists working radiantly. Security in a job is of great importance, yet principals may simply have a confined augmentation here.

There many areas wherever teachers and principals hold different views. Perhaps, the paramount impression is that some principals do not see their role as leadership from a position of positive affirmation however fall back on what may be a dictatorship. The other very robust feature of all the data is that the polarization of views, suggesting two different forms of the motivational atmosphere in several colleges. This desires any exploration. most significantly, setting up an environment of dependability wherever teachers will be feeling fully positive about their principal as a result of the principal views them is fundamental while this is often a better would like than simply being regardful, insightful, and kind-hearted despite the approach that these are important. As a result, this wherever there is trust, people feel regarded and wherever people feel regarded and teachers are motivated. So the learning organization and academic institutions are secured high rank due to these motivated and energetic teachers.

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